

11-16 AUGUST 2019
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on Composite Materials

Non-asbestos polybenzoxazine composites: friction and mechanical property

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Current Trends and Future Perspective of Friction Materials

Ref : G. Straffelini, R. Ciudin, A. Ciotti, S. Gialanella, *Environmental Pollution*, 207 (2015) 211-219.

Polybenzoxazine Literature

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Chapter 44

Polybenzoxazine-Based Self-Lubricating and Friction Materials

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Polybenzoxazine composite brake pads

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Mechanical Property and Friction Coefficient of Poly(BA-35x) Composites

Effects of short carbon fiber contents on the tribological characteristics and mechanical properties of the polybenzoxazine composites can be summarized as follow.

- The addition of short carbon fiber in the polybenzoxazine composites increased flexural strength and modulus of the composites.
- At a various temperature in a range of 100 – 350 °C, the friction coefficient of polybenzoxazine composite reinforced with the short carbon fiber at 25 % by weight (a mass ratio of aramid pulp:short carbon fiber = 75:25) increased up to a temperature of 300 °C and was still maintained at 350 °C.

Based on the findings in this work, the obtained polybenzoxazine composite has high potential to be used for friction materials where high friction coefficient and modulus are required.

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